

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 06th May 2024

Accepted: 14th May 2024

Online: 15th May 2024

KEYWORDS

Formative assessment, tests, quizzes, oral questions, diagnostic assessment, summative assessment.

MODERN FORMS OF ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11196004>

ABSTRACT

This article describes the essence and content of modern approaches to the assessment of students' knowledge, as well as the main differences between formative and summative assessment.

Today, changes are taking place in all areas of our society, rapid development is taking place to meet world standards. Including in the education system. On December 24, 2021, the head of our state signed two historic decisions on granting independence in financial, academic and organizational management to family educational institutions, which will bring fundamental positive changes to the family education system. This, in turn, requires a new system-based approach to the management of higher education institutions. Assessment is an important part of the educational process. Constantly monitoring the quality of education and the knowledge levels of students is the basis for introducing important innovations into the educational process. Today, based on the new system, various forms of assessment have been developed and are being presented to the educational process. One of these is formative assessment.

By assessment, we mean the process of comparing the child's current achievements (failures), previous achievements (failures), and the correlation of educational results with the norms established by the current educational standards. The process of creating evaluation criteria and forms is carried out together with students, and we consider this a way to build children's values. A set of formal and informal assessment methods adopted by teachers in the teaching process is called "Formative assessment". It is a part of the educational process carried out by teachers, aimed at improving the student's understanding and skills by changing the teaching and learning methods.

Formative assessment attempts to provide both teachers and students with direct and detailed feedback on student performance and learning. It is an ongoing process that monitors the needs and progress of students during the learning process. The main task of the formative assessment is to determine whether the goals set for the academic year have been

fulfilled or not. Therefore, both teachers and students should clearly know the educational goals that they want to achieve during the academic year.

Educational goals are officially reflected in the teacher's work plans. Or the teacher will be able to informally determine learning goals together with students.

Formative assessment begins with the idea that students should play an active role in the learning process. The steps (mechanisms) necessary to achieve the educational goal are clearly defined in the formative assessment. However, to achieve this, the assessment must be well designed. In this process, a lot of attention is paid to and encouraged to self-evaluation and cooperation among students.

Marina Aleksandrovna Pinskaya, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, researcher writes the following in the book "New Forms of Assessment":

Formative assessment is necessary to diagnose how the educational process is going not only at the final stage, but also at the initial and intermediate stages, and if the data turns out to be unsatisfactory, based on the obtained data, the necessary information changes can be made to include and improve the quality of educational activities. Formative assessment focuses on individual learning skills or skills within the curriculum rather than the curriculum as a whole. These assessments are designed to measure progress toward a specific goal, he says.

One of the most useful parts of formative assessment is that there is no single formative assessment method. Instead, there are hundreds of different assessment methods available. Each teacher can develop a deep repertoire of potentially formative assessments. In addition, teachers can adapt and modify formative assessments to meet the needs of their students. This is important because variation helps to engage students and ensures that the teacher's assessment of the concepts being taught is consistent. Having options also helps students see the types of assessment that naturally fit their personal preferences or strengths and weaknesses throughout the year.

The best formative assessment is engaging, adapting to students' strengths, and identifying areas that need additional instruction or support. Formative assessment is a proven learning tool that has a lot of value for teachers and students. Teachers can design and use formative assessment to guide future lessons, develop individual learning goals for students, and gain valuable information about the quality of instruction provided to students.

Teachers who use regular, continuous formative assessment in their classrooms find that student engagement and learning increase. Teachers can use information from formative assessment to modify instructional materials for both whole-group and individual lessons. Students benefit from formative assessment so that they always know where they are and become increasingly aware of their strengths and weaknesses. Formative assessments are easy to create, easy to take, easy to collect, and easy to use. In addition, they require a limited amount of time to complete. Formative assessments help students set individual goals and track progress on a daily basis.

There are a variety of formative assessment mechanisms that can be used in any classroom. Some of the more popular ones are:

1. Direct questioning or homework,

2. Journals of answers during the study process or assignments given during the lesson,
3. Control work conducted during the lesson,
4. Graphic organization or monitoring of students' activity in class,
5. Implementation of return communication,
6. Self-assessment of students,
7. The possibility of making changes to the educational process based on the result.

Formative assessment can also take the form of diagnostic tests, standardized tests, quizzes, oral questions, or written assignments. Formative assessment is carried out simultaneously with instruction. A common form of formative assessment is diagnostic assessment. Diagnostic assessment measures the student's current knowledge and skills in order to determine the appropriate program of study. Self-assessment is a form of diagnostic assessment that involves students evaluating themselves. Teachers should create and use the types of formative assessment that are most useful for students and necessary for educational activities. Formative assessments do not affect the final grades, and this allows students to remove the fear of mistakes that are inevitable during the initial assimilation of the material.

An important condition: for assessment to be truly formative, its results must be used by the teacher to adjust teaching. They should be communicated to the student and used for planning. Not only the teacher, but also the child should imagine what he needs to work on in the near future. Formative assessment focuses on determining students' understanding of instructions before summative assessment. Summative and formative assessment are often referred to in educational contexts as assessment of learning and assessment for learning.

Summative assessment. Summative Assessment means student assessment; it is result oriented. It is part of the evaluation process given to participants periodically, usually at the end of a course, term or unit.

The purpose is to check the knowledge of the students, that is, to check the extent to which they have learned the material they have been taught. Summative assessment seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of a lesson or program, examines the learning process, and so on. Scores, points, or percentages obtained as indicators of the quality of the curriculum and provide a basis for ranking schools.

Here we will consider the differences between formative and summative assessment. The main differences between formative and summative assessment.

1. Formative assessment refers to various assessment procedures that provide information required in the educational process and adjust teaching. Summative assessment is defined as a standard for evaluating students' knowledge.

2. Formative assessment is diagnostic, and Summative assessment is evaluative.

3. Formative assessment is an assessment for learning, Summative assessment is an assessment of education.

4. Formative assessment is carried out continuously on a monthly or quarterly basis. On the other hand, Summative assessment is done only after the completion of the course at certain intervals.

5. Formative assessment is conducted to improve students' knowledge. On the other hand, summative assessment is conducted to evaluate student performance.

6. Formative assessment was adopted to control students' knowledge. In contrast to summative assessment, it is aimed at evaluating students' knowledge.

7. Formative assessment grades are less than summative grades, because the grades obtained in the FA determine whether the students are promoted or not.

The main difference between these two assessment procedures is that while formative assessment is a type of learning process, summative assessment is an assessment process. Balanced assessment builds on both, providing necessary information about teachers' next steps and measuring students' knowledge of a content standard.

If we look at the education system of developed countries, for example in Great Britain, for helping staff (teachers) to learn and develop good practice in relation to educational evaluation by adults (leaders) in educational and educational settings, There is an award for education, assessment and quality assurance (TAQA). Therefore, assessment is the main process for the development of education. Especially formative assessment provides accurate information about the quality of education.

In summary, formative assessment should be a regular component of any classroom assessment.

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